

THE EFFICACY OF HYOSCINE BUTYLBROMIDE ADMINISTRATION BEFORE EMBRYO TRANSFER ON EMBRYO TRANSFER DIFFICULTY AND ICSI OUTCOME.

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Abstract

Background: The embryo transfer procedure is IVF's final and most crucial step (ET). The implantation rate and overall effectiveness of IVF can be influenced by a number of variables, including embryo quality, endometrial receptivity, and ET method. The use of ultrasound guidance, uterine contractions during ET, and the type of catheter used during the procedure are the three main factors that affect whether the treatment is successful or not. Therefore, it is preferable to prevent the start of uterine contractions when transferring the embryo.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of giving hyoscine butyl bromide before embryo transfer on the difficulty of embryo transfer and the outcomes of ICSI in ART cycles.

Materials and Methods: From October 2020 to April 2022, 80 infertile women undergoing ART cycles participated in this prospective, randomized clinical trial at the High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies/Al-Nahrain University. Recombinant FSH (Gonal-F) was used in a controlled ovarian hyperstimulation technique. The patients were randomly divided into two equal groups (n=40) after receiving written agreement. The first group got hyoscine, while the second received glucose water 5% as a placebo, 30 minutes before embryo transfer. The data was examined using Fisher exact tests, χ^2 , t-test, an ANOVA, by SPSS version 22.0.

Results: Pregnancy rates were 41.25% overall. Easy ET was significantly greater than difficult ET in the hyoscine group (56.7% versus 30%) than in the control group (43.3% versus 70%), with a p-value of 0.039. Analysis and comparison of the ICSI results between the two groups. Hyoscine significantly outperformed the control group in terms of implantation rate, clinical pregnancy rate, (IR ; 23 % versus 11%) p=0.040 , (CPR; 52.5 % versus 30 %)p=0.041 respectively and non-significant higher live birth rates (LBRs ; 81 % versus 50%)p=0.114 , there was also no significant difference between hyoscine and control group in miscarriage rate with the lowest rate in hyoscine group (19 % versus 50%) and p= 0.114.

Conclusion: By lowering uterine contraction and cervical muscular spasm, it appears that hyoscine butylbromide given 30 minutes before embryo transfer can significantly increase easy embryo transfer, implantation rate and clinical pregnancy rates with a non-significant rise in LBRs, and decrease miscarriage rate.

Key words: Embryo transfer, Hyoscine , Contraction , Clinical Pregnancy rate, ART.

1. Introduction

The rational treatment option for many infertility cases, especially in severe infertility factor, is assisted conception procedures that are collectively termed assisted reproductive technologies (ART) (Poulain M et al., 2021).

Effective implantation and pregnancy in phases of assisted reproduction depend on a variety of factors. It is known that the endometrium plays a crucial role during the so-called "implantation window". Loss of embryo implantation is one of the primary reasons for IVF failure. Implantation is influenced by the embryo's quality, activity, and embryo/endometrial interaction (Mahajan N and Sharma S., 2016; Makrigiannakis A et al., 2021). The direct influence of GnRH antagonist or agonist on the corpus luteum or endometrium, altered endometrial receptivity due to endometrial asynchrony, and early expression of pinopodes are all symptoms of high levels of oestrogen and progesterone (Craciunas L et al., 2019). The embryo transfer procedure is IVF's final and most crucial step (ET). The implantation rate and overall success of IVF can be affected by a number of variables, including as embryo quality, endometrial receptivity, and ET method (F Cirillo et al., 2020). Ultrasound guidance, uterine contractions during ET, and the kind of catheter utilized during the procedure are some of the most crucial elements that affect whether the treatment is successful or not (Conto et al., 2017). Therefore, it is preferable to delay the start of uterine contractions when transferring the embryo. The implantation and pregnancy rate reduces with increased myometrial contractions, according to real-time ultrasound scan analyses. Numerous elements and tocolytic medications have been shown to be capable of preventing these contractions. Hyoscine butyl bromide is one of the most effective medications that has been suggested to lessen uterine contractions (Zargar M et al., 2013). A peripherally acting antimuscarinic and anticholinergic inhibits postganglionic neurons' acetylcholine receptors, causing smooth muscles in the myometrium, gastrointestinal tract, and renal system to relax and contract (Maged AM et al., 2018). Recent studies have shown that hyoscine inhibits nicotinic receptors potently and non-competitively in vitro, providing a second mechanism of action for the medicines' spasmolytic effects (Zhu CP et al., 2017). A few earlier research look at how this medication affects embryo transfer (Sohrabvand et al., 2009; Zargar M et al., 2013). Since hyoscine has an antispasmodic effect, our extensive study investigates how it affects ART results with the aim of determining if it might lessen uterine contractions during embryo transfer and ease the difficulty of ET.

2. Materials and methods

A prospective, randomized clinical trial was done at the High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies/Al-Nahrain University from October 2020 to April 2022. A total of 80 women participated in this research. Each patient submitted written informed consent before participating in the trial, which was permitted by the Ethical Committee of the Faculty of Al Nahrain University's High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies. situations when ART was suggested by an infertility expert owing to ovulation abnormalities, tubal factors, unexplained infertility, minor cases of endometriosis, male factor, or

a combination of male and female factors and the patient was under the age of 40. Also all women with good quality embryos transferred were included. While cases of uterine abnormality were excluded, all cases were put on their first ART cycle. Controlled ovarian hyperstimulation was done. All patients were enrolled in flexible antagonist protocol, which started at day 2 of the menstrual cycle, an ultrasound examination was accomplished in order to exclude those women with ovarian cyst and to assess the endometrial thickness. It involved ovarian stimulation with gonadotropin (rFSH) (Gonal-F; Merck -Serono, Switzerland) beginning on the second day of the menstrual cycle, followed by the injection of a GnRH antagonist (Cetrorelix acetate for injection 0.25 mg: Cetrotide®, Merck, Switzerland), with the dosage of the Cetrorelix acetate injection 0.25 mg according to the size of the largest follicles when they reach 13–14 mm. Transvaginal ultrasound was done on 5th day of stimulation and subsequent scan was done every 2-3 days as necessary. The follicles growth was tracked by serum E2 level and transvaginal ultrasound till the day of hCG administration. Ovulation triggering was induced by the administration of (Ovitrelle) 250 microgram/0.5 ml s.c. (Ovitrelle®; Merck Serono, Switzerland) subcutaneously. Oocytes were retrieved by aseptic transvaginal ultrasound-guided oocyte aspiration, approximately 34–36 hours after Ovitrelle administration under general anesthesia. The swim up method was used for preparation of semen. The intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) technique was achieved (4–6) hours after oocyte retrieval to all patients. Around 12-17 hours after ICSI technique, fertilization was checked. Embryo development (cell quantity and degree of fragmentation) was measured 48 or 72 hours following insemination or ICSI (day 2 or 3). Following microinjection and embryogenesis, the research group (N=80) was randomly split into two groups A (N=40) and B (N=40). Half an hour before embryo transfer, group A got an infusion of hyoscine butyl bromide 25 mg over 20 minutes (Hyoscine butylbromide ampoule 20 mg, Julphar, Rass Al Khaimah, U.A.E.), whereas group B received glucose water 5% (Glucose 5%(W/V) 500 ml, B. Braun, Germany). Sonographic guidance was used to transfer the embryos. The patients were questioned on whether they experienced lower abdomen cramping or not. Following embryo transfer, all groups slept for two hours before being discharged. Age, BMI, the number of oocytes and embryos transferred, the endometrial thickness on the day of embryo transfer, the duration and cause of infertility (primary and secondary), the history of ART, basal hormonal analysis, the presence of cramps after embryo transfer, and other details were all recorded in the questionnaire. vaginal progesterone (400mg twice daily) has been supporting the luteal phase. After the embryo transfer, on day 14, a serum β -HCG test was performed. For the woman who later had a positive result, an ultrasound was done to objectively determine if there were 1 or 2 gestational sacs, which are indicative of clinical pregnancy (Pandey S et al., 2012). The data was analyzed by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. ANOVA, independent sample t-tests, chi square and Fishers exact tests. The findings were considered statistically significant whenever the p value was equal or less than 0.05. The study's primary goal was to assess the effect of hyoscine bytylbromide on embryo transfer difficulty and ICSI outcomes (implantation rate, clinical pregnancy rate, miscarriage rate, and live birth rate).

3.Results

A total of 80 ICSI cycles were enrolled and categorized randomly, divided into two groups (N=40) and available for investigation. Group A received hyoscine butyle bromide 25 mg infusion and group B placebo control group received glucose water 5%. The mean ages of group A was 29.48 ± 5.43 and group B 27.70 ± 4.35 years respectively. The mean body mass index (BMI) was A (24.73 ± 2.92) and B (24.77 ± 2.49 kg/m²) with no significance difference between 2 groups. The mean duration of infertility of women was significantly different $p=0.007$ and for A (7.95 ± 3.71) and B (5.90 ± 2.81). The two groups were found to be identical with no significance difference with respect to type of infertility and causes of infertility which were illustrated in table (1). There were significant differences in FSH, TSH, and E2 levels across groups when all of the patients in the two groups were stratified based on their basal hormonal levels, with p values of 0.032; 0.027 and 0.026 respectively, as shown in table (2). There were only significant variations in the mean number of grade I embryos and the number of gestational sacs when the two groups of cases were grouped by the oocyte and embryo characteristics, as shown in table(3), with p values equal to (0.003 and 0.045, respectively). There was a significant difference in embryo transfer difficulty and easy ET more than difficult in the hyocine group with ($p=0.039$) but no significant difference in day of embryo transfer and endometrial thickness, as shown in table (4), when the two groups of the cases were categorized by the characteristics of the embryo transfer day, day of embryo transfer and embryo transfer difficulty, and percentage of easy embryo transfer, respectively. The over all pregnancy rate was 41.25% and when the two groups of the cases were compared according to the ICSI outcomes ,the comparison of ICSI outcomes between hyoscine butylbromide and control group were illustrated in table (5) , the results showed significant higher implantation rates and clinical pregnancy rate (23 % versus 11% with $P=0.040$) and (52.5 % versus 30 % $P=0.041$) in hyoscine and control group respectively, however, there were no statistically significant differences in the rates of miscarriage and live births between the two groups, with the hyoscine butylbromide group having a lower miscarriage rate ($P=0.114$) and a higher live birth rate ($P=0.114$).

Table (1): Baseline characteristics for women comparable in the two groups

Variables	Hyoscine butylbromide group	Control group	P-value
Age (years)(Mean \pm SD)	29.48 ± 5.43	27.70 ± 4.35	0.111 t-test
BMI (kg/m ²)(Mean \pm SD)	24.73 ± 2.92	24.77 ± 2.49	0.948 t-test
Duration of infertility (years)(Mean \pm SD)	7.95 ± 3.71	5.90 ± 2.81	0.007* t-test
Type of infertility			
Primary (Number (%))	25(51%)	24(49%)	

Secondary (Number (%))	15(48.4%)	16(51.6%)	0.818(Chi-square test)
Cause of infertility (Number (%))			
Ovulatory	18(64.3%)	10(35.7%)	0.234(Fisher's Exact Test)
Tubal	6(37.5%)	10(62.5%)	
Male factors	9(40.9%)	13(59.1%)	
Unexplained	1(20%)	4(80%)	
Combined factors	6(66.7%)	3(33.3%)	

SD: Standard deviation; *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table (2): Basal hormonal level for women comparable in the two groups.

Hormones	Hyoscine butylbromide group	Control group	P -value (Independent samples t-test)
	Mean \pm Standard deviation		
FSH (mIU/ml)	6.24 \pm 2.07	7.14 \pm 1.60	0.032*
LH (mIU/ml)	5.39 \pm 1.67	5.83 \pm 2.48	0.357
Prolactin (mIU/ml)	15.19 \pm 5.30	13.35 \pm 5.63	0.136
TSH (mIU/ml)	1.71 \pm 0.70	2.09 \pm 0.82	0.027*
E2(Estradiol)(Pg/ml)	36.07 \pm 9.44	31.57 \pm 8.22	0.026*
Testosterone(mIU/ml)	0.72 \pm 0.28	1.11 \pm 2.09	0.250
AMH (ng/ml)	2.66 \pm 1.26	2.78 \pm 0.88	0.316

SD: Standard deviation; *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant).

Table (3): Oocyte and embryo characteristics among women comparable in the two groups

Variables	Hyoscine butylbromide group	Control group	P -value (Independent samples t-test)
	Mean \pm Standard deviation		
Oocytes number	10.48 \pm 4.88	9.53 \pm 4.26	0.357
Metaphase I (MI)	2.23 \pm 1.56	2.03 \pm 1.45	0.555
Metaphase II (MII)	6.65 \pm 2.82	6.80 \pm 3.09	0.821
Germinal vesicle (GV)	1.20 \pm 1.22	0.70 \pm 1.06	0.055
Number of injected oocytes	6.33 \pm 2.54	6.88 \pm 2.80	0.361
Number of fertilized oocytes	5.60 \pm 2.19	6.13 \pm 2.68	0.341

Embryos number	5.58 ± 2.14	5.90 ± 2.60	0.544
Grade I embryo	2.33 ± 0.94	1.70 ± 0.85	0.003 *
Grade II embryo	2.17 ± 1.05	2.10 ± 0.98	0.744
Number of transferred embryos	3.08 ± 0.61	3.28 ± 0.67	0.171
Number of gestational sacs	0.70±0.79	0.38±0.62	0.045 *

SD: Standard deviation; *: *p* value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table(4): Embryo transfer day characteristics with embryo transfer difficulty among women comparable in the two groups

Variables		Hyoscine butylbromide group	Control group	P-value
Continuous variables (Mean ±SD)				t-test
Endometrial thickness (mm) at day of embryo transfer		8.71 ± 0.95	8.68 ± 0.93	0.860
Categorical variables		Number (%)		Chi-square test
Easy or difficulty of embryo transfer	Easy	34(56.7%)	26(43.3%)	0.039 *
	Difficult	6(30%)	14(70%)	
Day of embryo transfer	Day 2	14(60.9%)	9(39.1%)	0.217
	Day 3	26(45.6%)	31(54.4%)	

SD: Standard deviation; *: *p* value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table(5): Intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) outcomes between hyoscine butylbromide and control groups.

ICSI outcome	Hyoscine butylbromide group	Control group	<i>P</i> -value
Implantation rate (N %)	28/123(23%)	15/131(11%)	0.040 * (Chi-Square test)
Pregnancy rate (N %)	21/40(52.5 %)	12/40(30 %)	0.041 * (Chi-Square test)

Miscarriage rate (N %)	4/21 (19 %)	6/12(50 %)	0.114 (Fishers Exact Test)
Live birth rate (N %)	17/21 (81%)	6/12(50 %)	0.114 (Fishers Exact Test)

SD: Standard deviation;N:Number; *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

4. Discussion

Endometrial receptivity, embryo quality, and using all necessary precautions during embryo transfer procedures are the main factors influencing conception (Eftekhar M et al.,2020). Numerous studies have been conducted in this area to improve the efficiency of embryo transfer. Absence of uterine contractions at the moment of embryo transfer is one factor that greatly affects endometrial receptivity (Saravelos and Chiu Li., 2019).

According to the current study, the pregnancy rate was significantly higher in the hyoscine group (52.5%) than in the control group (30%). This may be attributed to a significant increase in easy ET as compared to difficult ET in the hyoscine group as compared to the control group, which was consistent with findings from Candido Tomás et al. and P E Levi Setti et al. that easy transfers increased pregnancy rates by 1.7 times as much as difficult transfers (Candido Tomás et al.,2002; P E Levi Setti et al.,2021) additionally, the use of tocolytic medications helped with ET challenges and mitigated the effects of cervical spasm and uterine contractions, comparable to (Zargar M et al., 2013), albeit there is also conflicting evidence (Tur-Kaspa et al., 1998; Burke et al., 2000; Heitmann, R J ET AL.,2017). We are aware that different doctors may use different methods for transferring embryos, which might affect the results. The reduced pregnancy rate in challenging embryo transfers might be attributed to a number of things. The likelihood of implantation may be reduced if the cervix is lacerated or the endometrium in the uterine fundus is touched. (Singh N et al.,2012). Regarding to the effect of hyoscine butylbromide on ICSI outcomes, it was significantly increase implantation rate, CPR and non- significantly increasing LBRs while it decreasing miscarriage rate although it was non-significant . In a study done by BH Kadhim et al., on the effect of piroxicam there was a similar result in that it increase IR , CPR and LBRs and decrease miscarriage rate (BH Kadhim et al.,2021). Also other study similar with us, Sohrabvand et al., compared between indomethacin and hyoscine administration of 25 mg, 30 minutes before embryo transfer and found significant beneficial increase in pregnancy rates by decreasing cervical muscle spasm and uterine contractions and then increase cumulative reproductive outcomes (Sohrabvand et al.,2009). According to Kido et al., reducing uterine peristalsis with the use of an anticholinergic agent during IVF treatment may help retain embryos and increase the likelihood of a successful pregnancy in fresh ET cycles as well as in women who have experienced multiple ART failures, reducing stress on the embryo and possibly enhancing ET success (Kido et al.,2009). Other studies agree with us in its tocolytic effect (Burke et al., 2000; Sirohiwal et al.,2004; Nakai et al.,2008; Zhu CP et sal.,2017). Hyoscine, an anti-muscarinic medication, reduces cervical spasm by limiting the muscarinic actions of acetylcholine on autonomic variables (Burke et al., 2000). Instead, as previously described, hyoscine's physiological anticholinergic properties may be to

blame for its positive benefits. Additionally, a research by Zhu CP et al., has demonstrated that in vitro, hyoscine potently and non-competitively inhibits nicotinic receptors and this explain a second mechanism of action for the spasmolytic effects of the drugs. Hyoscine butylbromide inhibits acetylcholine at parasympathetic sites in smooth muscle and secretory glands (Zhu CP et al.,2017). There are other drugs that might lessen uterine contractions before embryo transfer. Atosiban was linked to better ART cycle results, according to research by Schwarze JE et al., which may have therapeutic importance (Schwarze JE et al., 2020). However, a contradictory recent study reveals that giving piroxicam to women undergoing IVF and frozen-thawed ET had no positive impacts on the pregnancy rate (Zarei A et al.,2021). Despite lowering uterine cramps, indomethacin does not significantly affect the pregnancy rate, according to the findings of a research by Bernabeu et al. (2006). Although NSAIDs theoretically prevent platelets from aggregating by inhibiting COX and thromboxane, which would enhance blood flow, it appears that they may have negative effects on the inflammatory processes required for implantation (Bernabeu et al.,2006).

Age, BMI, the causes and length of infertility, baseline hormonal level, endometrial thickness on the day of transfer, oocytes, embryo features, and the day of embryo transfer were among the variables studied in our study to determine their relevance to the success of ART. The significant differences was in mean age with the lowest age in control group and since all the patient enrolled in our study less than 40 years old and although the hyoscine group older than control group the effect of hyoscine drug antagonized this differences in age and change the result and this was similar to Zargar M et al., study (Zargar M et al.,2013), despite the effect of age in some studies suggested that increase maternal age may be associated with poor pregnancy outcome and decrease the fertilization rate (Pierce & Mocanu., 2018). Regarding BMI, there was no statistically significant difference and it was roughly the same, which was consistent with other findings that revealed BMI had no significant impact on the pregnancy rate or the quantity of mature oocytes (Banker et al., 2017; Vilarino et al., 2011) .Which was in contrast to some studies showed that BMI was associated with reproductive problems (Mena et al. 2020). In the present study, it was found that the percentage of women with primary infertility more than secondary infertility with no significant difference ,a similar result was found by (Benksim et al.,2018). Regarding the causes of infertility lack of significance result showed agreement with the research done by (Deshpande and Gupta., 2019). There were substantial disparities in the lengths of infertility across the research groups, with the control group suffering from shorter durations, comparable to Zargar M. et al. study (Zargar M et al.,2013). This difference can be due to the younger age in control group and also the causes that resulted in prolong infertility and recurrent implantation failure like immunological , nutritional and genetic factors, endometriosis, endocrine diseases, maternal chronic diseases in addition to unexplained infertility and this difference was antagonized by the effect of tocolytic drug. Regarding the basal hormonal level the significant differences between groups were in FSH, and TSH both hormone were higher in control group but within normal value, while E2 was more in hyoscine group than control group but it was within normal level. When euthyroid women undergoing IVF/ICSI had high TSH levels (TSH level >2.5 mIU/L), neither the

clinical pregnancy rate nor the miscarriage rate changed (Jin L et al., 2019). There was a negative association between the basal follicular stimulating hormone level and the no. of follicles and no. of oocytes and number of grade I embryo and pregnancy rate so affect ICSI outcomes (Mukheef M et al., 2021). Age-related basal FSH concentrations are an excellent predictor of ovarian responsiveness to assisted reproductive therapy. High FSH levels in young women may have an impact on labor and delivery parameters but not pregnancy rates. Normal FSH levels in elderly women may increase "avorted" cycles but may not improve ICSI results. Younger women with high FSH levels had higher pregnancy and childbirth rates than older women with normal FSH levels (Kdous M et al., 2016 ; Salama S et al., 2021). To evaluate ovarian reserve, basal FSH levels work better than early follicular estradiol (E2) levels alone. Poor intra- and inter-cycle dependability characterizes basal E2. When FSH levels are normal and basal E2 levels are high (>60–80 pg/ml), this may signal poor response and higher cycle cancellation rates (Rasool, S and Shah D, 2017).

Regarding oocyte and embryo characteristics the only significant differences was in the mean number of grade I embryo and mean number of gestational sacs which was higher in hyoscine group than control group and this put our study in agreement with Sivrikoz et al., (2021) who found that significant high number of grade one embryos mean a good quality oocytes might fertilized and gave a good quality embryos that resulted in higher gestational sacs, improved implantation rate and higher pregnancy rate concluded that good quality embryos positively affect the pregnancy rate and ICSI outcomes (Sivrikoz et al., 2021). Regarding ET day, the current study show no significance difference between the study groups although most ET done at day 3. As a result, on day 3 as opposed to day 2, the physiology of the intrauterine environment is more favorable for the growing morula (Bastu E et al., 2013). Delaying ET may thus be desirable in general if in vitro culture results in acceptable embryo development (Lee JW et al., 2017). There were no discernible changes in endometrial thickness across the research groups on the day of embryo transfer, which had no bearing on the results of the groups. This was comparable to earlier studies such as (Jassim et al., 2021). Other studies have estimated that clinical pregnancy rate decreased when the EMT was < 7 mm (Eftekhar et al., 2018).

In the present study, hyoscine proved to have a good safety profile. One patient had nausea, whereas the other patients had not developed any side effect which was similar to Sohrabvand et al., (Sohrabvand et al., 2009). The purpose of this study was to evaluate and compare the effects of administering hyoscine prior to embryo transfer on ICSI-ET results and embryo transfer procedure difficulties in ART cycles because there are little data on the influence of hyoscine or similar group of medicines on ART outcome.

Conclusion

Hyoscine butyl bromide appears to be significantly increase easy embryo transfer, implantation rate, pregnancy rates with non-significant increases in LBRs, and decrease miscarriage rate by lowering uterine and cervical muscular spasm 30 minutes before embryo transfer.

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Author Contribution

Fahad IA , performed the study, examined and reviewed results, and manuscript writing with the help and supervision of LA Al-Anbari, and S Muayad

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Clearance

The study was approved by the Ethical Approval Committee.

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